

Possible Antituberculous Compounds. Part XIII. Preparation of Aryl Thiosemicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazones

V. S. Misra and R. S. Varma

Five new aryl thiosemicarbazides and twenty-nine corresponding new thiosemicarbazones have been synthesised with a view to testing their tuberculostatic activity.

The discovery of Tibione (*p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone¹) as a reputed clinically active tuberculostat, brought to the forefront thiosemicarbazones as a group of antitubercular agents. Since then numerous tuberculostatic thiosemicarbazones have been prepared by various workers². Encouraged with this fact, we have also prepared a number of thiosemicarbazides and corresponding thiosemicarbazones.

These compounds have been prepared by following the method of Kazakov and Vostovskii³. The initial amine was treated successively with CS₂, ClCH₂COONa, and N₂H₄·H₂O. The thiosemicarbazides were either obtained during the reaction or crystallised on cooling. These thiosemicarbazides were then condensed with different aromatic aldehydes to furnish the thiosemicarbazones.

The antitubercular activity of these compounds will be reported later on.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aryl Thiosemicarbazides.—The initial amine (0.006 *M*) was dissolved in ethanol and NH₄OH (conc., 13.5ml) added to it. In case the amine was used as a hydrochloride, a two-

1. Domagk, *Schweiz. Z. Path. Bakt.*, 1949, 12, 575.

2. Behnisch *et al.*, Ger. Pat. 852086/1952; 874140/1953; 889894/1953; Trove, *Univ. Milan Farmaco (Pavia) Ed. Sci.*, 1960, 15, 468, 474.

3. *Iz Vest. Tekhnol.*, 1961, 4, 238.

fold amount of NH_4OH was taken. The reaction mixture was cooled below 30° and CS_2 (5ml) added during 15 mins. with rapid shaking. After complete dissolution of CS_2 , the solution (or the suspension of the dithiocarbamate) was allowed to stand for 1 hour and then added to an aqueous solution of the sodium salt of monochloroacetic acid. During condensation of the dithiocarbamate, the mixture usually got warm and changed colour from red to yellow. To the warm solution 50% hydrazine hydrate (6.5 ml) was added. The mixture was cooled and the product separating was filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

Aryl Thiosemicarbazones.—To a boiling solution of an aromatic aldehyde (0.005M) in ethanol the appropriate thiosemicarbazide (0.005 M) in ethanol was added. The mixture was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hour on a steam bath. It was cooled, filtered, and recrystallised from ethanol.

TABLE I

Aryl thiosemicarbazide.

No.	Aryl amine.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -Aminodiphenyl	C_{12}H_9	245°	55%	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	17.63	17.28
2	<i>p</i> -Aminodiphenyl amine	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}$	$120-25^\circ$	50	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	21.32	21.70
3	<i>p</i> -Aminoacetophenone	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}$	115°	60	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{S}$	22.02	21.31
4	<i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$	220°	45	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$	19.46	19.90
5	3-Aminoquinoline	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{N}$	$180-85^\circ$	53	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	25.52	25.88

TABLE II

Aryl thiosemicarbazones.

No.	R'.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
			R = C_{12}H_9 .			
1	C_6H_5	175°	95%	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	12.50	12.61
2	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	108°	98	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.62	12.17
3	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	125°	90	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{S}$	11.30	11.63
4	<i>o</i> - OHC_6H_4	135°	90	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}_2\text{S}$	12.50	12.10
5	<i>m</i> - OHC_6H_4	101°	85	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}_2\text{S}$	12.45	14.89
6	<i>p</i> - $\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	235°	88	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{S}$	14.63	11.49
7	<i>o</i> - ClC_6H_4	140°	80	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{ClS}$	11.81	11.76
8	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CH}$	82°	88	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.64	11.26
9	<i>p</i> - $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	171°	70	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	10.90	
10	C_6H_5 $\begin{cases} \text{OCH}_3(m) \\ \text{OH}(p) \end{cases}$	168°	95	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$	11.68	11.13

TABLE II (contd.)

R'	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
				Found.	Reqd	
R = C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N.						
11	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	*158-60°	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ ClS	14.36	14.71
12	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	251°	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ON ₄ S	15.34	14.89
13	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	145-50°	98	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	17.39	17.93
14	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	265°	50	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	16.15	15.55
15	<i>p</i> -C ₃ H ₇ C ₆ H ₄	205°	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ S	13.92	14.43
16	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH	85°	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	15.73	15.05
R = C ₈ H ₇ O.						
17	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	176°	95	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	12.42	12.84
18	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	196°	98	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	12.80	13.41
19	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	201°	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ S	15.95	16.37
R = C ₇ H ₅ O ₂ .						
20	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	*205°	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	15.73	16.27
21	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	237°	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	12.83	12.76
22	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	158°	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	13.46	13.33
23	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	225°	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	13.56	13.33
24	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	192°	92	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	12.20	12.59
R = C ₉ H ₆ N.						
25	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	166°	98	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	16.23	16.66
26	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	201°	88	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	16.95	17.39
27	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	*252°	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₅ S	19.32	19.94
28	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	241°	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	16.90	17.39
29	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	205°	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	17.12	16.44

*Decompose on heating.

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Errata

Page.	Line.	Read	For.
19		As comp. No. 4 in Table I was not mercu- rated, compounds 4-8 in Table II to be read as compounds No. 5-9.	
130	14	(40 ml)	(10 ml)
143	3	$[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\text{NH}_3]_2$	$[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\text{NH}]_2$
289	Formula XVIIb . to read as		
		<p>The structure shows a five-membered thiazole ring with an oxygen atom at the top position. At the 2-position of the thiazole ring, there is a pyridine ring. The pyridine ring has a hydroxyl group (-OH) at its 3-position. The thiazole ring has two hydroxyl groups (-OH) at the 4 and 5 positions. A hydrogen atom (H) is explicitly shown at the 4-position, and another hydroxyl group (-OH) is shown at the 5-position.</p>	
422	1*	2-acetamido-4-benzoyl- 5-chloromercuri and 5-bromo thiazoles etc.	2-acetamido5- chloro and 5-bromo- mercuri thiazole etc.
423, 424	Table II	2-acetamido-5-bromo	2-acetamido-5-bromo*

* From bottom.